

Humanistic Foundations of Information Science in an Age of Data Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

A tension exists in information science (IS) between the scientific approaches and aspirations of the field's members, many of whom identify with disciplines such as computer science, and the field's long humanistic traditions, most notably in librarianship and bibliography as they intersect with areas of study such as history and literature. Bush's "Memex vision," as just one example, imagines IS as a "scientific" discipline. It is a vision, as the scholar of information history Paul Duguid (2021) has shown, "fostered increasing elision between descriptions of people and machines" (p. 248). This panel investigates elisions such as these and the tensions in IS between modes of scientific investigation and humanistic modes of knowing. Through presentations on bibliography and hermeneutics as they can be understood from diverse cultural and historical perspectives, this panel explores some of the humanistic foundations of information science in an age when intelligence is readily associated with data and science rather than culturally specific methods of human interpretation and understanding.

KEYWORDS

Humanities, Theoretical Foundations, Information Science, Bibliography, Hermeneutics, Knowledge Organization

INTRODUCTION

The technological or computing tradition has been emphasized in information science research for more than eight decades. Empirical and the positivist methods are prioritized in the field. Objectivity and neutrality are expected and extolled. This emphasis is in tension with a desire to know and explore human methods of interpretation and meaning-making. This panel explores this tension and suggests ways that the humanistic foundations of information science can be brought more productively into view. The presentations were selected to illustrate three different ways to provide a more diverse and more complete understanding of the humanistic foundations of information science: philosophical hermeneutics as humanistic foundations of information science; reinvigorating bibliography in the digital age; hermeneutical understanding of main branches of information science.

SECTIONS

Philosophical Hermeneutics as Humanistic Foundations of Information Science, presented by Lin Wang.

Hermeneutics is the outcome of the humanistic spirit development in the Western world. It is the philosophical basis of humanities. In the second half of the 19th century, the emergence of the independent "Geisteswissenschaften" required breaking the chauvinism of natural science and establishing a philosophical foundation for itself.

Hermeneutics addressed this need. Modern hermeneutics, as the philosophy of humanities, has been further developed and strengthened by Gadamer and others. As far as information science is concerned, it has a solid humanistic nature in essence. Although hermeneutics was introduced into information science as early as 1980's (Benediktsson, 1989), it has not drawn a lot of attentions in the IS academia. Modern hermeneutics, as the metatheory of information science, can strengthen the humanistic foundation and develop the humanistic spirit of the discipline. Capurro (2000), Hansson (2005), Day (2010), Wang (2012), Kelly (2016), Gorichanaz (2019) and others have contributed to the exploration in this research aspect. Several topics are discussed in this panel: the research focus of information science should be shifted from information artifacts to humans and their interactions with information during information processing and utilization. Historical, social, and cultural contexts are the determinants of sense-making and prerequisites to understanding information behavior. The status of tradition (social) and authority should be enhanced in information science. It is necessary to develop metadocumentation to meet this goal. The restoration of the phronesis (practical wisdom) proposed by Aristotle has unique implications for IS. The emphasis on the status of phronesis enables IS to combine research and practice more closely, thus realizing the fundamental purpose of any information practice work: find and discover meaning.

Reinvigorating Bibliography, presented by Wayne de Fremery, explores what might be gained by reconsidering bibliography as infrastructure for information science. The presentation describes how processes and modes of

thinking associated with what has been called systematic, descriptive, analytical, and critical bibliography are integral to practices and modes of thinking in the broad field of information science. It makes the case that although foundationally supportive of information science, bibliography is marginal in the field in at least two senses. As infrastructure, bibliographical practices are peripheral means serving what are considered more powerfully important ends. Bibliography is also powerfully marginal in information science in the old sociological sense of having multiple identities. As the presentation will aim to show, core bibliographical processes, such as enumeration, description, analysis, and critique, are central to a variety of practices and areas of study in the field where they are referred to by a variety of different names including (but hardly limited to) cataloging, informatics, information retrieval, big data, and artificial intelligence. The presentation concludes by suggesting that a reconsideration of bibliography as a foundation of information science can help those in the field better account for how the IS asserts truth, affect beliefs, and instantiates knowledge with(in) evolving socio-technological and cultural systems.

Information Science and Hermeneutics, presented by Luciana Cortes Mendes, discusses how information behavior can be understood from the perspective of philosophical hermeneutics. Drawing from Heidegger's (2015) concept of *Dasein*, a "particularly human way of existing" (Dreyfus & Wrathall, 2005, p. 3-4), and what characterizes it, as well as from Gadamer's understanding of the hermeneutic circle, the presenter argues that the manner humans interact with information is a hermeneutic endeavor. Following this argument, the presenter explores how information as thing, documents (Buckland, 1991), can be thought of within a hermeneutical understanding of information behavior. Subsequently, the presenter explores how document storage, organization and retrieval can be understood as fundamentally hermeneutical activities, concluding that philosophical hermeneutics provides a theoretical framework of reference for the development of a metatheory of information science.

STRUCTURE

This moderated panel session will have four parts: Three short presentations followed by a period for question and answer and for comments from participants.

The moderator will be Michael Buckland, Emeritus Professor, School of Information, University California, Berkeley.

PANELISTS

There will be three panelists, all of whom are SIG HFIS officers, in the following order:

Lin Wang is distinguished professor of information science, Hangzhou Dianzi University, China. He is also a guest research fellow in the National Information Resource Management Institute at Beijing. He received a Young Information Scientist award from the China Society for Science and Technology Information and his PhD in information science from Peking University. His research interests include the foundations of information science and information philosophy. He has published more than eighty academic papers in international LIS journals and leading peer-reviewed information science journals in China. Several papers received "best paper" awards by national academic organizations including the Chinese Society for Science and Technology Information and the Chinese Science and Technology Communication Society. Professor Wang currently is the Chair of SIG HFIS ASIS&T.

Wayne de Fremery is Professor of Information Science and Entrepreneurship and Director of the Francoise O. Lepage Center for Global Innovation at the Barowsky School of Business, Dominican University of California, USA. Professor de Fremery was previously an associate professor in the School of Media, Arts, and Science at Sogang University in South Korea. He currently represents the Korean National Body at ISO as Convener of a working group on document description, processing languages, and semantic metadata (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 34 WG 9). His recent research projects have concerned "Digital humanities in the iSchool" (JASIST, 2022), "Copy theory" (JASIST, 2022), "Context, relevance, and labor" (JASIST, 2022), as well as the use of deep learning to improve Korean OCR, for which he received a national citation of merit from the South Korean Ministry of Culture, Sports, and Tourism. His panel topic is the subject of a book forthcoming from the MIT Press. Professor de Fremery currently is the Chair-elect of SIG HFIS ASIS&T. More at www.pwdef.info.

Luciana Cortes Mendes is a public librarian at Monteiro Lobato Library in Guarulhos, Brazil. She was a part-time lecturer in Library and Information Science at University of São Paulo, Brazil, and Digital Information Curation at Centro Universitário Assunção, Brazil. She has a Ph.D. in Information Science from University of São Paulo, Brazil, and was a Visiting Student Researcher at University of California, Berkeley. Her research interests include

hermeneutics applied to Library and Information Science, Document Theory, history and foundations of Library and Information Science, and Knowledge Organization. Dr. Mendes currently is the secretary of SIG HFIS ASIS&T.

CONCLUSION

This panel session will be an in-depth investigation of the humanistic foundation of information science in an age of data intelligence. The panelists will contribute insights that are expected to be new to all or most of the audience: the significance and implications of hermeneutics to information science research; reinvigorating bibliography to account for how we assert truth, affect belief, and instantiate knowledge with(in) social and information infrastructures. Time will be reserved for discussion.

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